

THE IMPORTANCE OF EDUCATING YOUTH IN THE SPIRIT OF NATIONAL VALUES

Bolkiyev Akhmad Begali o'g'li

Teacher of Jizzakh State Pedagogical University

Abstract. This article provides information about folkloric works in primary classes and ways and methods of educating them in the spirit of national values through folklore works.

Keywords. Folklore, elementary class in the textbook tools, national ability, education, methods.

The educational process requires every teacher and pedagogue to have great intelligence, patience, fortitude, high love for students and their profession. The teacher must always be in search, gain knowledge and experience, deeply understand students, notice their inner world, control their growth and development levels and help with words, work or practical action when necessary. The ability to receive are factors that ensure the success of the education and upbringing process.

A teacher's personality is a stable system of socially significant qualities characterizing him as a person. A teacher's dedication to his profession and understanding of its social importance, influence on children and sympathy with them is a set of qualities that, when combined with the teacher's work and communication, integrity of the teacher's work is achieved.

In order to carry out such responsible tasks, the employees of the preschool educational institution are responsible for implementing the historical experience of the Uzbek people regarding education.

Therefore, we should approach the spiritual and material heritage of our ancestors from the point of view of inheritance and educate the young generation right from preschool educational institutions.

Because of our people to his creed according to " Human power is in education ". In this respect compared to Medium Asia peoples, including Uzbek People have their rich historical, spiritual and cultural history inheritance, thousand years during content found education actions, traditions, morals rules to the treasury has That 's it of the people great thinkers perfect a person especially his morality about to the world famous great thinkers perfect a person especially his morality about to the world famous has been a masterpiece works writing left until school education from institutions our grandfathers left great from inheritance use, education methods use them children to his mind absorb important important has Such Yusuf Khos from

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

inheritance Hajib's " Kutadgu". Bilik ", Kaikovus's " Kabusnoma ", Ahmad Yugnaki's "Bahoritsion ", A. Navoi's " Mahbub - ul-Qulub ", Devani's " Ethics " Jalali ", Husayn Preacher " Futuvvatnoma " of Koshifi Like "Sultani ". unique , rare from his works use We believe that it is permissible .

Our grandfathers the child each bilaterally wake up to develop big attention they looked That is why in our republic healthy generation bring up in order to raise a child state policy level raise and to him patriotic , loving , humanitarian by doing to educate before school at the age of , start and him non-stop continue carry on school , family , neighborhood public organizations from attention aside not stay is emphasized . So until school education in institutions children from their earliest years grandfathers to his heritage relied on without each bilaterally development main We consider it one of the tasks .

Ethical education content : whole polite person to form directed .

Ethical brought up in person stable spiritual motives formed will be Ethical concepts different young in groups formation level is different . Children is mastering moral feelings , experiences spiritual faith of formation important from the conditions is one It is a moral feeling of a person to society , to people , to himself relatively emotional attitude means These people between treatment in the process to the body will come and develops . Feelings moral knowledge and beliefs with closely connected goes Ethical emotion them bring up separately separate the rest society not this understanding person needs his knowledge and experiences his intuition based on to the body will come and develops . The identity of the child in education pedagogical effect to show method , styles different ways work exit is necessary pedagogues moral feelings to educate big attention in aging their in his opinion , good feelings root since childhood Beginning need

People , kindness , cooperation union benevolence , in work in worries around the world beauty about care to do excitement in the process to the body will come . Ethical habits moral Beliefs are feelings with one in line behavior internal regulators to the system enters

Get started class " Reading book in textbooks proverb dry alone without being quoted , maybe to him suitable narrative and fairy tales is given

For example, 4 th grade " Read winter " To Chakimchi " in the book reward " story let's take A student this the work full by reading from the exit after bite bad vice that it is people between break it , in the story to the governor unfaithfulness what he did and the end in consequence punishment received ie the gallows that he was hanged knows This is the story through student " Vadaga Loyalty is a brave man work ", Chakimchi egg pochog is his place tandiz - hearth ", like proverbs the meaning easily understand they get

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

Salt This is also the case in the story " Haqi " (4th grade) . The story read after division , sakvol and assignments with is processed . In question 3 it is like this it is said : " Salt. " fertility about how proverbs you know " Salt for a day tired instead hello forty days Give " , " Salt eat to the saltiness do not spit " and others

3rd grade " Winter in his book Farhad Musajonov's story " Goodness ". given The boy is him reading , " Goodness on the ground won't stay " , " Good intention is half state " , " From the good there is a garden - from the bad there is a stain " , " For the good if you approach , you will be enough good , bad if you approach you stay shame " , " Good the dish earth , bad head " ,

" Good it sucks bad turns off " , " Good honorable , bad good " , " Good grudge impossible , bad grudge You can tell by the eyes of a bad boy from the word " , " Good If so, it's bad if trouble " , " Good with if you walk safe it 's bad with if you walk bad you will be " .

" Goodness do it to the river horse fish knows , fish if he doesn't know Halik knows ." (Halik is God from the names one) as proverbs they get to know each other and the meaning understand they are enough . Proverbs people is wisdom . In it of people his life ok follow , experience collected said wise words own expression found Compact most of the time poetic way expression done of proverbs the theme is colorful . It cannot be denied ripe level from advice consists of will be For example:

Garden el - fat el

Knowledge in power - power in knowledge

Written literature its manifestations are also different comments sure and compact expressing as proverbs sermano proverbs Primary 2nd grade students in education " Navoiy wisdom they learn For example :

" From the world carefree pass if you say , science craft learned " , " Patience know a lot depends the work opens , at work in love a lot "

Proverbs and wise words second , third , fourth class " Reading topics in the book concluding , his spiritual content student in his memory long keeper genre as given From him except 3rd graders , " People oral creativity in the column given friendship , harmony , science about people proverbs they learn People proverbs and wise words memorize students thinking grows his speech enriches his life denial reached can't be marriage experiences to master help will give .

In textbooks fast to say and great for riddles attention given These are also popular creativity genres being , students mind sharp to do , to burro his tongue intended . Quick in saying something one sound repeat , reader fast to say talk by heart in it known one the sound right pronunciation reach to the skill achieves

Children's game " Svetafor ". playing the body they rest their sorrows spirits is triggered , the game condition as follows: Readers sitting in places of the teacher to his words attention with ear they put " red when it is called "lamp " . to the rule according to right sitting down get ,” yellow when it is called "lamp " . slap playing, green and in " light ". legs is moved .

Students not to be distracted to the error road not to put they strive From this then , cluster method with new topic statement will be done

LIST OF REFERENCES .

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev " National development our way persistence with continue it 's new to stage ko ' taramiz " - Tashkent, " Uzbekistan ", 2017 , page 592 , page 10.
2. SH.M.Mirziyoyev " Preschool education system management radical improvement remedy Decree No. PF-5198 on 30.09.2017, pp . 7-8.
- 3 . BRDjurayeva , HMTojiboyeva , GMNazirova " Before school education to children aged education of giving modern trends " – Tashkent, UzPFTTI publishing house, 2015, page 198.
4. Muslimov NA " The future occupation education teachers professional formation” / Monograph.– Tashkent .: Science , 2004, 360 pages.
5. Saidahmedov N.” Pedagogical skill and pedagogical technology " . - Tashkent: "Science and technology"- 2003, 340 pages.
6. R. A. Mavlonova , N.H.Rakhmonkulova , K.O.Matnazarova , M.K.Shirinov , S.Hafizov " General pedagogy " - Tashkent, "Science and technology " publishing house, 2018, 530 pages.
- 7.Safarov, B.N. (2022). PEARLS-ADVANCE IN THE STUDY OF INTERNATIONAL READING LITERACY. Innovative development in educational activities, 1 (5), 134-138.
8. Safarov, B.N. (2022, November). EFFECTIVENESS OF ORGANIZING PEDAGOGICAL COACHING IN PRESCHOOL EDUCATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS. AT THE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INNOVATIVE EDUCATION IN THE 21ST CENTURY (Volume 1, Issue 8, Pages 30-35).
9. Safarov, B. (2021). Importance of mathematics lessons in preparing 6-7 year old children for school education: Importance of mathematics lessons in preparing 6-7 year old children for school education. Journal of Early Childhood Education, 2 (2).

THE MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY

VOLUME-4, ISSUE-3

10. Turakulov X.A, Bukhtakov S. Civilizational Pedagogical Systems-Intellectualization Of Educational Content As A Didactic Basis //International Scientific and Current Research Conferences. - 2020. - S. 145-147.
- 11 . Boltakov S.X. STAGES OF FORMATION OF CIVILIZATION PEDAGOGICAL SYSTEMS //Science and innovation. - 2022. - T. 1. - S. 262-265.
12. Bol'ltakov SX Practical aspects of using civilized pedagogical systems in the training of future primary school teachers //Journal of Innovation, Creativity and Art. - 2023. - T. 2. – no. 3. - S. 71-73.
- 13 . Norboyevich, Safarov Botir , and Nabiyeva Gulnara . " IMPORTANCE OF DIDACTIC GAMES IN THE MENTAL EDUCATION OF PRIMARY CLASS STUDENTS." CONFERENCE OF NATURAL AND APPLIED SCIENCES IN SCIENTIFIC INNOVATIVE RESEARCH . Vol. 1. No. 1. 2024.

